

Vertiport Location Planning for Urban Air Mobility Airport Shuttle Services under Uncertainty

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Highlights

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- Risk-based two stage model for vertiport site selection & VTOL fleet optimization
- Real-world case study shows counterintuitive vertiport placements can be beneficial
- Risk hedging lowers the probability of losses under uncertain demand
- Minimal profitability impact of route extensions due to airspace restrictions
- Prioritizing maximum speed in VTOL model selection offers limited economic benefit

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Abstract

In recent years, the number of electrical vertical take-off and landing vehicle (eVTOL) designs and start-ups has significantly increased.

However, operators face several challenges during the piloting and implementation of an eVTOL service. Besides regulatory and safety concerns, one key question is how to implement a profitable operation of a fleet of eVTOLs given uncertain customer adoption considering available transport alternatives. The main investment decision in the strategic planning phase involves the number and location of vertiports to build in the network, as well as the number of vehicles to provide in the fleet.

In this work, we propose a risk-averse two-stage-type optimisation model for an eVTOL airport shuttle service as the most likely initial Urban Air Mobility use case to be implemented. In the first stage, a strategic decision on the number of eVTOLs and number and location of vertiports in the urban area and at the airport site must be made under uncertain demand. In the second stage, the operational phase of the chosen vertiport network is optimised for a materialized demand scenario. We use an optimal learning framework to evaluate the expected performance of different first-stage decisions. We test our model in a case study with real-world data from a large European hub airport deriving recommendations for policy makers and fleet operators. We show that there are some non-intuitive vertiport placement decisions, prove the advantage of a risk-averse approach in highly uncertain settings and demonstrate the impact of different eVTOL operations parameters on the average expected profit.

Keywords: eVTOL, urban air mobility, vertiport network planning, airport shuttle

1. Introduction

Electrical vertical take-off and landing (eVTOLs) aircraft are seen as a new disruptive means of transportation, which should revolutionize and elevate Urban Air Mobility (UAM) (Garrow et al., 2021). For the last five decades, conventional helicopters have been the driving force of UAM, carrying passengers within large cities and between downtown and airports in Los Angeles, Chicago, New York, and San Francisco, on the international route between Brussels Airport and Lille, and even as a regular service connecting London Gatwick and Heathrow airports (Pak et al., 2024). Currently, the company BLADE provides regular airport shuttle services between Manhattan and JFK or Newark airports and Nice and Monaco in Europe, with the long-term goal of making aviation more accessible by preparing for the adoption of eVTOL aircraft (Blade Air Mobility, 2021). BLADE, as well as eVTOL manufacturers and other UAM stakeholders, claim that eVTOLs have significant advantages over conventional helicopters in terms of noise, emissions, and costs, advertising them as comparatively superior options for UAM services, especially for airport shuttles (Blade Air Mobility, 2021; Holden and Goel, 2016).

Airport shuttle services appear to be one of the use cases with the highest benefits, lowest risks and highest viability for the initial introduction of an eVTOL supported UAM service in 2025 to 2030, as revealed by the European Union Safety Agency (EASA) study on the societal acceptance of UAM in Europe (EASA, 2021). Several European airlines, such as Wideroe, Virgin Atlantic, and Air Greenland have announced their intentions to join forces with eVTOL manufacturers to start airport shuttle services (Air Greenland, 2022; American Airlines, 2023; Archer Aviation, 2023; Delta, 2023; Eve, 2023; Virgin Atlantic, 2025). UrbanV, a company founded for the development of Advanced Air Mobility (AAM) infrastructure by Aeroporti di Roma, SAVE Group, Aeroporto di Bologna and Aeroports de la Côte d'Azur, have already built a test vertiport at Rome Fumicino Airport, with plans to develop the vertiport network in Italy (UrbanV, 2025).

However, there is some skepticism regarding the timeline, scope, and viability of different UAM services (Arc Aero Systems, 2023), especially in light of recent insolvency filing of two of the most prominent European eVTOL manufacturers Lilium and Volocopter (Aviation Week, 2025), who were also involved in many infrastructure development projects in Europe (EASA,

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2021). Infrastructure development, that is, finding suitable locations for vertiports, which ensure safe operations and viable service, is often considered among the biggest challenges for the success of future airport shuttle services (Brunelli et al., 2023a; Holden and Goel, 2016; EASA, 2021). Prospective UAM airport shuttle service providers and local authorities face a decision problem about a potential investment in vertiports in urban areas, while airports have to decide where to build vertiport(s) at airport locations or its vicinity. The decision about possible major investments needs to be taken under uncertain demand for the UAM airport shuttle service. In addition, the demand attracted by the service will strongly depend on the number and location of vertiports, as their placement determines the total travel time, and to an extent the cost of service, which are arguably the most influential demand factors (Brunelli et al., 2023b; Long et al., 2023).

Therefore, the main motivation behind our work is to design a stochastic risk modelling framework to support strategic decision-making for UAM airport shuttle services. We develop a mathematical model to identify the best set of vertiport locations in a given urban area and at the airport grounds, as well as the number of eVTOL aircraft subject to uncertain demand for the service. UAM stakeholders and prospective UAM airport shuttle operators can use the model to effectively quantify the impact of hedging risk of over- or under-provision of capacity, i.e., the number of vertiports and eVTOLs, thus allowing them to make informed decisions to trade-off risk. This risk of investing in excess or insufficient resources/capacity is a highly relevant issue in transportation, arising from the demand uncertainty. This challenge is evident in sectors such as freight transportation (cargo airlines, third-party logistics providers), on-demand mobility services (including air taxis), and contexts involving the introduction of new services, routes, or fleets. At workshops on UAM, industry practitioners stressed the importance of considering uncertain demand and customer adoption, since there is no existing previous experience with UAM eVTOLs implementations up to date. Our results from workshops are confirmed by recent literature on risk-adversity in eVTOL operations, i.e., by Sun et al. (2025).

To demonstrate the practical use of the model, we use a real-world case study of the Madrid Metropolitan Area and Adolfo Suárez Madrid-Barajas Airport. We present actionable recommendations for different stakeholder groups and policy makers based on the insights gained in our numerical experiments: Increased ground turnaround times (ground times hereafter) between eVTOL flights can have a negative impact on the viability of the service, but this aspect can be mitigated by investing in and deploying more eVTOLs without large losses in profitability.

Potential deviations from the shortest route between two vertiports due to, e.g., governmental restrictions on flight corridors, has lower impact on the average profits, therefore leaving sufficient room for designing a safe UAM route network. Also, lower eVTOL aircraft cruise speed does not reduce profit much for the service provider if the service is offered within a 50km radius around the airport. While our model is able to hedge against the risk of negative profits in highly uncertain settings, decision makers need to carefully choose their level of risk adversity since risk hedging leads to lower average profits.

This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we review and discuss the relevant literature in the field of vertiport location optimisation, two-stage optimisation algorithms, and risk management. In Section 3, we formally develop the two-stage optimisation problem. In Section 4, we introduce a simulation optimisation approach to solve the two-stage optimisation problem. We use real-world data from a European hub airport in Section 5 to test our developed framework against an intuitive location optimisation benchmark algorithm to derive managerial insights regarding the number of vertiports and eVTOLs and the impact of different airport-site vertiports on overall performance. Conclusions and a perspective on future research are provided in Section 6.

2. Literature Review

In this section, we provide a brief overview of the most relevant recent publications addressing the problem of selecting the number of vertiports and their (approximate) locations and highlight our progress vs. state of the art. For detailed reviews, the reader is referred to Long et al. (2023) for UAM analysis, to Brunelli et al. (2023a) for vertiport locations and capacity, to Garrow et al. (2021) for demand modelling, infrastructure, and operations, while an overall review of current UAM literature can be found in Straubinger et al. (2020).

2.1. Vertiport location optimisation

On the one hand, one of the most prevalent methods for determining vertiport locations seems to be clustering algorithms (Long et al., 2023), which generally group individual or aggregated demand points into individual clusters to identify locations for vertiport placement. Hwang et al. (2019) use geographical coordinates of commuting data from the capital of South Korea - Seoul as input to k-means and argue that obtained cluster centroids represent reasonable approximate

locations for vertiport placements. Guo et al. (2025) compare five different clustering techniques for vertiport location selection and assess their efficiency in terms of travel time savings, accessibility improvements and transport equity. Based on the Munich Metropolitan Area case study developed by Ploetner et al. (2020), Guo et al. (2025) find that a k-means algorithm with enhanced centroid initialization yields better accessibility results compared to Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), agglomerative hierarchical clustering, Gaussian mixture model (GMM), and mean shift clustering.

On the other hand, Macias et al. (2023) argue that the vertiport placement problem should generally be defined as a facility or hub location problem, in which the location(s) of the hubs is determined to meet an objective function. Daskilewicz et al. (2018) developed a vertiport model that assumes that short-term demand for eVTOLs is driven by high-income car users with long travel times and identify that the majority of urban UAM trips are below 30 miles long. This is similar to the findings of Wei et al. (2020) and Wu and Zhang (2021). Rath and Chow (2022) present a single-allocation p-hub median location problem studying two alternative objectives: maximising ridership and maximising revenues for a forecasted demand. Willey and Salmon (2021) propose a single-allocation p-hub median location problem with modifications to consider multi-leg trips and the probability of passenger travel, among other features.

There are also a few works combining the two above-mentioned approaches. Holden and Goel (2016) apply k-means clustering to geographical locations of the origin-destination commuter points in the first stage to reduce the number of candidate locations to be considered in the second stage using integer programming. Sinha and Rajendran (2022) propose a two-phase location optimisation model, which first identifies potential locations with a warm start algorithm considering socio-economic factors such as rental cost, population density, number of taxi trips, average salary and road facility. The output of this model is used as input for a k-means constrained clustering algorithm to determine the optimal vertiport locations.

Regarding the publications addressing specifically vertiport selection for the UAM airport shuttle service, there are also a few publications which deploy different modelling approaches. Roy et al. (2022) develop a scheduling optimisation model to maximise the realized demand for an airport shuttle taxi in Atlanta. The optimal vertiport locations are chosen based on a simple combinatorial approach to maximise the number of customers. A multi-commodity network flow framework is employed to find an optimal flight schedule. They conduct a sensitivity analysis

of demand on ticket price and present an estimation for the optimal fleet size based on a small case study in the Atlanta metropolitan area with 4-5 eVTOLs. Lv et al. (2024) develop a mixed integer linear programming model to optimise the routing and scheduling of passengers for an airport shuttle service, including vehicle balancing. They apply the model in a case study for Beijing Capital International Airport and derive insights on demand and response, as well as the influence of vehicle speed on system operations, among others.

Wang et al. (2022) develop a modelling approach to optimise the number, locations and capacities of vertiports including strategic considerations such as fleet size planning, passenger pooling, etc. Customer demand is modelled as a Poisson process and a queueing network is used to estimate operating profits from flights. They propose an approximation algorithm for the nonconvex demand function and discuss insights on the profitability of UAM networks. In contrast to their approach, our model focuses on generalizable insights for an eVTOL airport shuttle service - not on a classical UAM network - under high demand uncertainty considering risk adversity. We develop a simpler model with high scalability, enabling the solution of large problem instances with respect to the number of candidate vertiport locations. Moreover, due to the exclusivity of the airport shuttle service offered, we will not allow any grouping of passengers. The charging of eVTOLs can happen in the ground time between two flights in which the passenger is entering/exiting and receiving safety instructions. Our assumptions and parameter choices are based on discussions with industry professionals.

Lastly, Morscheck et al. (2025) consider four different vertiport locations at Frankfurt airport as potential candidate locations to integrate an UAM airport shuttle service line to Frankfurt Trade Fair. They show that a high volume of eVTOL operations could be integrated with the airline operations for all locations, subject to their assumed safe separation. While the focus of Morscheck et al. (2025) is on evaluating the feasibility of the UAM airport shuttle for one airport-city line with three proposed corridors using simulation, we develop a model which selects vertiport locations among a set of predefined approximate locations in the urban area and exact locations at the airport.

In this paper, we define the problem of selecting vertiport locations in the urban area and at the airport location as a two-stage optimisation problem. The decision for the first stage – the number and location of vertiports, as well as eVTOL fleet size – must be taken under uncertain demand for the UAM airport shuttle service, before a second stage problem, i.e., scheduling of

eVTOL aircraft, can be solved. We also consider a risk-averse service provider who would make an investment decision and commence a service only if the probability of profitable operations is above a set threshold.

2.2. *Two-stage risk-averse optimisation problems*

The newsvendor problem is the most prominent two-stage problem and is intensively studied in the literature, e.g., by Qin et al. (2011). In this problem, a buyer is stocking up an inventory under uncertain demand with the aim to maximise profit by procuring the optimal number of products to sell. After this decision, demand realizes, and the buyer sells the products for a price. In such problems, the usual approach is to evaluate multiple different demand materialization scenarios and select a subset which performs best on average. Another approach, called robust optimisation, e.g., pursued by Gabrel et al. (2014), includes uncertainty and risk into the modelling of real-world optimisation problems to consider the worst-case scenario. Chance constrained programming, developed by Charnes and Cooper (1959), introduces a constraint holding a certain condition with a specified probability to account for risk. Value-at-Risk modelling includes a risk constraint on the objective function ensuring that the value of the objective function is higher/lower than a certain threshold for a set probability. This approach has been incorporated into the newsvendor problem by researchers by adding a risk-constraint on the realized profit of the buyer. The problem is intensively discussed by Özler et al. (2009) and Lin et al. (2022).

Contrary to a typical risk-averse newsvendor problem, in our problem the quantities (vertiport locations and eVTOLs) purchased by the decision maker are not sold, but their capacity is used to gain revenue, and there is no “salvage value” of unused capacities. Within the aviation industry, Künnen et al. (2023) takes a similar approach to solve a two-stage newsvendor problem for the allocation of airspace capacity under uncertain air traffic demand. Also, Starita et al. (2020) optimise required man-hours of air traffic controllers for a similar problem. In both works, a strategic decision - the airspace capacity and number of air traffic control sectors to be open - must be taken under uncertain future air traffic demand. After the decision has been taken and the demand is realizing, the demand routing and delay allocation problem is solved. They use an asymptotically optimal set (AOS) framework based on the works of Hu and Andradóttir (2019) as a random search method for a sample average approximation (SAA). We adopt this approach for our problem of selecting the number and location of vertiports across the urban area and at the airport.

Van Oosterom and Mitici (2023) develop a two-stage optimisation model for the battery charging and swapping infrastructure for electric short-haul aircrafts. They propose a mixed integer linear program (MILP) managing the charging schedule of the aircraft batteries which is then used as a sub-routine by a master-problem determining the most cost-effective infrastructure. Although the structure of the MILP and the application is different, we also use the basic concept of this approach in our work.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no publications which have considered the problem of vertiport site selection for UAM airport shuttle service based on comprehensive real-world data and a case study for a major European airport in collaboration with experts from UAM and other relevant fields. We are the first to provide some generalizable insights to be used by fleet operators and practitioners to assess this eVTOL application, based on our real world data and methodology. While the methodology is mostly based on existing approaches, our insights are valuable for practice since our model solves a stylized risk-averse two-stage newsvendor problem to support strategic decision-making for vertiport placement and eVTOL aircraft fleet sizing needed for a profitable service, while considering uncertain demand and risk of capacity over- or under-provisioning.

3. Problem statement

We consider an UAM airport shuttle service provider (which also acts as the eVTOL fleet operator) as a strategic decision maker. The UAM airport shuttle service provider is investing in both the vertiport locations and the fleet of eVTOLs. This service provider can also be a joint venture of several providers co-funding the infrastructure and vehicles. The service provider's objective is to maximise the profit of the airport shuttle service including the initial investment in infrastructure and vehicles. The cost to build a vertiport in the urban area is exogenous since it is influenced by several characteristics, e.g., subsidies from local governments. The price depends on the area where the vertiport is built, the number of chargers and if the vertiport is on the ground or elevated. Furthermore, the exact locations of the vertiports in both the urban area and at the airport site highly affect the total travel time of the passengers influencing their choice of transportation mode.

Since the decision maker faces possible under- or over-provisioning of capacity, i.e., number of vertiports and eVTOLs, which highly affects the profit, they want to minimise the respective

risk. The structure of our problem is similar to a risk-averse newsvendor problem as discussed in Subsection 2.2. The problem consists of two stages: In the first stage, the decision maker needs to decide on the number, position and static capacity of vertiport locations (the number of eVTOL stands) as well as fleet size, i.e., the number of eVTOLs for the future service. This decision has to be taken while not exceeding a given investment budget.

In the second stage, uncertainty regarding demand materializes. Based on the strategic decisions taken in the first stage and the realized demand, the decision maker needs to decide on the flight scheduling with the objective to maximise the profit of the operations.

We visualize our two-stage optimisation model in Figure 1 and then explain the two-stages and their inner optimisation.

Figure 1: Visualization of proposed two stage optimisation model

3.1. First stage strategic newsvendor problem

Let $G(S | x, N)$ be the expected profit of an operation of the subset of locations for vertiport construction $x \in X$ and the number of eVTOLs N for a given period of time. The subset of built vertiports is called vertiport network in the following. S represents a random scenario of the materialization of uncertain demand for the UAM airport shuttle service out of all possible demand scenarios \mathcal{S} , whereas the number of all possible scenarios can be infinite. The decision maker's objective is to maximise the expected profit over a large number of (demand) scenarios $S \in \mathcal{S}$ by deciding on a subset of vertiport location-capacity combinations x and a number of eVTOLs N , as shown in Eq. (1). If a vertiport-capacity combination $j \in J$ is built, $x_j = 1$, with J being the total number of possible vertiport-capacity combinations. A vertiport-capacity

combination j at location $l \in L$ has capacity q_j and associated cost $c_j \in c_J$, with c_J being a column vector containing the cost of all vertiport-capacity combinations J . The set of all possible vertiport-capacity combinations j at location l is denoted as Q_l . We ensure by Eq. (4) that only one vertiport-capacity combination j is selected per location l .

The cost for each eVTOL is c_v . The cost c_j and c_v represent the depreciation cost of each vertiport-capacity combination j and each eVTOL for the service provider for a given period of time that must not exceed a given investment budget B , Eq. (3). Using this formulation, we focus on a flight schedule for a given period of time and are able to compare recurring profits from operations with recurring costs for vehicles and infrastructure in the form of depreciation.

Moreover, the decision maker is risk averse, so we include a value at risk (VaR) constraint, Eq. (2), ensuring that the probability of achieving a profit lower than a certain threshold G_0 is below a level $\alpha \in (0, 1]$. The full first stage optimisation problem is depicted below:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{x, N} \mathbb{E}_S[G(S | x, N)] - c_J^T x - c_v N & \quad (1) \\ \text{s.t. } \mathbb{P}_S[G(S | x, N) - c_J^T x - c_v N < G_0] \leq \alpha & \quad (2) \\ c_J^T x + c_v N \leq B & \quad (3) \\ \sum_{j \in Q_l} x_j \leq 1 \quad \forall l \in L & \quad (4) \\ x_j \in \{0, 1\}^J & \quad (5) \\ N \geq 0, & \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

with x as our decision column vector with value 1 in the rows of specific vertiport location-capacity combinations j which are decided to be built.

3.2. Second stage tactical cost evaluation

The second-stage problem represents the tactical model in which the decision makers decide on the flight scheduling. We formulate the tactical problem as a mixed integer linear program (MILP). From the first stage of the problem, we have information on the vertiport locations, their capacities and the fleet size.

Demand in scenario S materializes in the form of a set of passengers I arriving throughout a time horizon T with time stages $t \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$. Passenger $i \in I$ arrives at time t_i^a at vertiport O_i

with the intention to travel to destination D_i and has a known profit margin of p_i . When passengers arrive at the system, the decision maker has to decide whether the passenger demand can be fulfilled based on available capacity or not. If passengers can be served, they are assigned to an eVTOL. Given the exclusivity of the offered service comparable with a chauffeur limousine service, we do not allow pooling of passengers, meaning that each passenger requires an individual eVTOL. Moreover, we do not include active rebalancing of vehicles in the optimisation model, but allow empty flights between the vertiports to serve upcoming customer requests. These simplifications of the model are made to reduce complexity to obtain a scalable model as well as to put the focus of our work on the two-stage risk-component of the model.

We introduce a set of binary decision variables for the assignment of passengers to eVTOLs similar to the approach of Bertsimas et al. (2019) from the field of vehicle routing to ensure a continuous network flow. If passenger i is transported by eVTOL $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ as the first passenger in the time horizon, $y_{n,i}$ equals 1. If passenger i is transported directly after passenger $i' \in I \setminus \{i\}$ on an eVTOL, $z_{i',i}$ equals 1. If a passenger i is not served due to capacity constraints, then $\sum_n y_{n,i} + \sum_{i'} z_{i',i} = 0$. The set of scheduling constraints is the following:

$$\sum_n y_{n,i} + \sum_{i'} z_{i',i} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in I \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_i z_{i',i} \leq 1 \quad \forall i' \in I \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_i y_{n,i} \leq 1 \quad \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_j P_{nj}^0 = 1 \quad \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \quad (10)$$

$$P_{nj}^0 \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \forall j \in J \quad (11)$$

$$z_{i',i} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in I \setminus \{i'\}, \forall i' \in I \quad (12)$$

$$y_{n,i} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \forall i \in I, \quad (13)$$

with P_{nj}^0 being a binary decision variable that indicates if eVTOL n is at vertiport j at time stage $t = 0$.

We include constraints on the start time of the individual flights. We assume that customers in this exclusive segment of transportation are not willing to wait, so there is a set starting time which equals the arriving time t_i^a of passenger i . The expected flight time from a vertiport j to

another vertiport j' is $d_{jj'}$. For the vertiport layout, we will assume independent multifunctional Final Approach and Take Off pads are used, as we outline in Section 5.2 in detail. The static capacity of a vertiport is set equal to the number of its pads. If customer i is served after customer i' , then the arrival time of customer i is at least the soonest time point at which it would be possible for the eVTOL to finish the previous job, come to the origin O_i of customer i and complete necessary ground time d^g , as depicted in Eq. (14). The ground time d^g needed between the arrival of an eVTOL at a vertiport and its departure with a customer. This time represents passenger processing (disembarkig, embarking and pre-flight briefing), as well as any extra time needed to charge the eVTOL.

The time constraint is also created for first flights if the eVTOL is not located at the same vertiport as the origin O_i of its first passenger as expressed in Eq. (15). Note that Eq. (15) is non-linear but can be easily linearized. If the destination of customer i' equals the origin of customer i , then $d_{D_{i'}O_i} = 0$. The set of time constraints is denoted as:

$$t_i^a \geq (t_{i'}^a + d_{O_{i'}D_{i'}} + d_{D_{i'}O_i} + d^g) \cdot z_{i',i} \quad \forall i, i' \in I \quad (14)$$

$$t_i^a \geq y_{n,i} \sum_j d_{jO_i} \cdot P_{nj}^0 \quad \forall i \in I, n \in N. \quad (15)$$

In addition to the scheduling of passengers and time constraints, we have to ensure that the capacity limits q_j of each chosen vertiport-capacity combination j are met. It must be ensured that the capacity limit q_j must not be exceeded at each vertiport j at every time stage t . The number of eVTOLs at a vertiport consists of the initial number of eVTOLs at the start of the shift in addition to the incoming eVTOLs over time minus the outlying eVTOLs over time:

$$\begin{aligned} q_j \geq & \sum_{n=1}^N P_{nj}^0 + \sum_{n=1, i \in \{I: D_i=j, t_i^a + d_{O_i D_i} + d^g \leq t\}}^N y_{n,i} + \sum_{n=1: P_{nj}^0=0, i \in \{I: O_i=j, t_i^a \leq t\}}^N y_{n,i} \\ & + \sum_{i' \in \{I: D_i=j, t_i^a + d_{O_i D_i} + d^g \leq t\}} z_{i',i} + \sum_{i' \in \{I: D_{i'} \neq j, t_{i'}^a \leq t\}, i \in \{I: O_i=j\}} z_{i',i} \\ & - \sum_{n=1, i \in \{I: O_i=j, t_i^a + d^g < t\}}^N y_{n,i} - \sum_{n=1: P_{nj}^0=1, i \in \{I: O_i \neq j, t_i^a - d_{D_{i'} O_i} < t\}}^N y_{n,i} \\ & - \sum_{i' \in \{I: O_i=j, t_i^a + d^g < t\}} z_{i',i} - \sum_{i' \in \{I: D_{i'}=j, t_{i'}^a - d_{j O_i} < t\}, i \in \{I: O_i \neq j\}} z_{i',i} \quad \forall t, \forall j. \quad (16) \end{aligned}$$

In total, there are four terms describing inbound vehicles, namely first flight assignments with the destination vertiport j , first flight assignments for passengers currently located at vertiport j served by an eVTOL not at j and the same for subsequent flight assignments. These four parts also build the number of outbound vehicles. The assumption for these constraints is that an eVTOL which flies empty to a vertiport j to pick up a passenger i starts at the latest possible time stage and arrives at vertiport j exactly at the time t_i^a when passenger i is supposed to start the flight.

The objective is to maximise the obtained profit margin of the eVTOL service

$$G(S | x, N) = \sum_i \left(\sum_{n=1}^N y_{n,i} + \sum_{i'} z_{i',i} \right) \cdot p_i, \quad (17)$$

with p_i being the approximated profit margin of flying passenger i from their origin to destination including the revenues and direct and indirect cost of operation (e.g., personnel, electricity, etc.).

The full integer program is formulated in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & G(S | x, N) \quad \text{Eq. (17)} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \text{passenger sequence constraints Eq. (7) - (13)} \\ & \text{start time constraint Eq. (14) - (15)} \\ & \text{vertiport capacity constraint Eq. (16).} \end{aligned}$$

The strategic model is complex to solve because the exploration of all possible demand scenarios for all possible vertiport location and capacity subsets is prohibitively computational expensive.

Therefore, we propose an approximate solution to the presented two stage newsvendor problem in the next section.

4. Approximate solution via simulation optimisation

The classic approach to approximation of a hard-to-evaluate expectation is to use sample average approximation. We likewise do this, however, we combine it with a learning framework so as to reduce the computational time. The idea is to quickly evaluate a given first-stage solution (i.e., the decision on vertiports and fleet) by discarding poor solutions quickly, not wasting much computational effort on evaluation of the expectation if there is statistically a small chance of this

solution to be a good one. Powell and Ryzhov (2012) refer to this as simulation optimization, which can be seen as a multi-armed bandit problem which is described in detail by Mahajan and Teneketzis (2008). In a multi-armed bandit problem, we aim to optimally allocate resources among competing projects. In simulation optimisation, the resources are the available computing power of the simulation and the projects are represented by different possible solutions to the first-stage problem of the newsvendor formulation.

4.1. Asymptotically optimal set framework

Our goal is to find vertiports x^* and fleet size N of eVTOLs so as to maximise expected profit subject to the risk constraint. To simplify the notation, we denote the result of the first stage optimisation $G(S | x, N) - c_f^T x - c_v N$ as $f(x, N, S)$. Any scenario S denotes a materialization of unknown demand across the urban area over the observed time horizon. Our approach balances exploration (searching for new possible good solutions of the first-stage problem) and exploitation (evaluating the available solutions in more depth to assess their quality).

We adapt the asymptotically optimal set framework from Hu and Andradóttir (2019) as shown in Algorithm 1. The aim of this algorithm is to iteratively create a list $X_k^* \subset X$ of promising solutions (with k being the number of solutions sampled), which is eventually reduced via exploitation to the optimal solution (x^*, N^*) . Within each iteration u , a new candidate solution is evaluated (exploration) or an existing promising solution is reassessed based on new scenarios S (exploitation). To balance exploration and exploitation, we only sample new solutions in iterations where $u = \lfloor k^{1.3} \rfloor$ and resample existing solutions otherwise, as done by (Künne et al., 2023).

To explore the full solution space of possible promising solutions to the first stage problem fulfilling the budget constraint when sampling a new solution, we use a combination of latin hypercube sampling approach shown in Algorithm 2 to ensure stratification across all dimensions and a local neighbourhood search. After a number of γ_{lhs} iterations in which new solutions are sampled via latin hypercube sampling, there are γ_{local} iterations in which new solutions are sampled from the neighbourhood of the current best performing solution $(x^*, N^*)_u$. With this technique, we not only explore the full solution space, but also ensure a local search within the most promising solution to find eventually the best network as a subset of all possible locations.

Once a new possible solution is sampled, we evaluate the new solution based on a benchmark scenario S_1 . If the profit of the new solution for scenario S_1 is at most λ worse than the average

Algorithm 1 Exploration-Exploitation framework to seek optimum vertiport configuration and number of eVTOLs based on the approach of Hu and Andradóttir (2019)

1: **Input:** Scenarios S , solution space X only including solutions satisfying budget constraint, sampling and resampling strategy

2: Initialize: $u = 0, k = 1, X_0^* = \emptyset, \hat{f}_0(x^*) = -M$ (negative large number)

3: **while** $\exists(x, N) \in X_k^* : W(x, N) < W_{\max}$ **do**

4: $u = u + 1$

5: **if** $u = \lfloor k^{1.3} \rfloor$ **then**

6: Select $(x, N) \in X$ based on sampling strategy, evaluate $f(x, N, S_1)$ and set $k = k + 1$

7: **if** $\hat{f}_u(x^*, N^*) - f(x, N, S_1) < \lambda$ **then**

8: $X_k^* = X_{k-1}^* \cup \{(x, N)\}, \hat{f}_i(x, N) = f(x, N, S_1), W(x, N) = 1$

9: **else**

10: $X_k^* = X_{k-1}^*$

11: **end if**

12: **for** $(x, N) \in X_k^*$ (ensure minimum amount of resampling) **do**

13: **if** $W(x, N) < \lceil k^{0.5} \rceil$ **then**

14: Set $\theta = \lceil k^{0.5} \rceil - W(x, N)$

15: valuate $f(x, N, S_{W(x, N)+1}), \dots, f(x, N, S_{W(x, N)+\theta})$

16: Update $\hat{f}_u(x, N) = \frac{\hat{f}_{u-1}(x, N)W(x, N) + \sum_{h=1}^{\theta} f(x, N, S_{W(x, N)+h})}{W(x, N) + \theta}$

17: Update $W(x, N) = W(x, N) + \theta$

18: **end if**

19: **end for**

20: Update $(x^*, N^*)_u = \arg \max_{(x, N) \in X_k^*} \hat{f}_u(x, N)$

21: **for** $(x, N) \in X_k^*$ (discard poor solutions or not satisfying risk constraint) **do**

22: **if** $\hat{f}_u(x^*, N^*) - \hat{f}_u(x, N) > \lambda/k^{0.15}$ **or** $\mathbb{P}_{W(x, N)}[f(x, N, S)] < G_0 > \alpha$ **then**

23: $X_k^* = X_k^* \setminus \{(x, N)\}$

24: **end if**

25: **end for**

26: **else**

27: Select $(x, N) \in X_k^*$ based on resampling strategy and evaluate $f(x, N, S_{W(x, N)+1})$

28: Update $\hat{f}_u(x, N) = \frac{\hat{f}_{u-1}(x, N)W(x, N) + f(x, N, S_{W(x, N)+1})}{W(x, N) + 1}$, and $W(x, N) = W(x, N) + 1$

29: Update $(x^*, N^*)_u = \arg \max_{(x, N) \in X_k^*} \hat{f}_u(x, N)$

30: **end if**

31: **end while**

32: **Output:** Optimal vertiport configuration x_u^* and number of eVTOLs N_u^* with average profit $\hat{f}_u(x^*, N^*)$

Algorithm 2 Latin Hypercube Sampling for Mixed Variables

- 1: **Input:** Number of samples γ , Number of dimensions d
 - 2: Initialize X as an empty $\gamma \times d$ matrix
 - 3: **for** $u' = 1$ to d **do**
 - 4: Generate a random permutation $\pi_{u'}$ of $\{0, 1, \dots, \gamma - 1\}$
 - 5: **for** $k' = 1$ to γ **do**
 - 6: $X[k', u'] = \frac{\pi_{u'}[k'] + U(0,1)}{\gamma}$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **for** $k' = 1$ to γ **do**
 - 10: Sample random number of eVTOLs $N_{k'}$ and append to $X_{k'}$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: **Return** X
-

of the current best solution at iteration u $\hat{f}_u(x^*, N^*)$, we add this solution to our set of promising solutions X_k^* . Additionally, with an increasing number of promising solutions, we remove poor solutions performing $\lambda/k^{0.15}$ worse in average than our current best solution $\hat{f}_u(x^*, N^*)$ or if the solution is not fulfilling the risk constraint Eq. (2). Over the course of the algorithm, the threshold $\lambda/k^{0.15}$ strongly decreases to reduce X_k^* to eventually one optimal solution.

When resampling existing solutions in the latter part of the algorithm, we apply an epsilon greedy approach as a resampling strategy. We resample a random solution $x \in X_k^*$ with probability $\sigma(k) = 0.99/k^{0.5}$. With probability $1 - \sigma(k)$ we evaluate new scenarios not for a random solution but for the best current solution $(x^*, N^*)_u$. After defining a solution to be updated, we evaluate this solution for a new scenario S , update the evaluation count $W(x, N)$ and the average profit $\hat{f}_u(x, N)$ of that solution. As done by Künnen et al. (2023), the algorithm is stopped if all candidates in the set of promising solutions have been evaluated over W_{max} scenarios.

4.2. Approximating second-stage optimisation MIP

The proposed mixed integer program presented in Section 3.2 can be solved to optimality only for small instances in a reasonable time. Due to the capacity constraints on the vertiport locations, the constraint coefficient matrix is not totally unimodular, making it challenging to solve. Since the evaluation of the second stage problem has to be solved multiple times for

different networks as part of the AOS framework depicted in Algorithm 1, we propose a simple heuristic that balances the travel time of the eVTOLs to the origins of the passengers and the overall profit by minimising a trade-off function. The heuristic is shown in Algorithm 3. At each time step, the heuristic selects the most promising feasible passenger for each eVTOL based on a comparison value that penalizes longer travel times and rewards higher profits. The algorithm ensures that passengers are either served on time or rejected while capacity constraints are fulfilled over the entire time horizon.

Algorithm 3 Profit and travel time balancing heuristic for evaluating second stage

- 1: **Input:** Passengers i with arrival times t_i^a , origin O_i , destination D_i , profit p_i
 - 2: Initialize: Available times $T_{\text{avail}} \leftarrow [0 \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}]$, Capacity tracker $Q_{\text{tracker}}[t][j] \leftarrow q_j$ for all t and j minus initial eVTOL positions P_n^0 of all eVTOLs N
 - 3: **for** time step $t = 0$ to T **do** Select a number of unassigned requests I_t
 - 4: **for** each eVTOL $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ **do**
 - 5: $i_{\text{best}} \leftarrow -1, v_{\text{best}} \leftarrow \infty$
 - 6: **for** each request $i \in I_t$ **do** Compute earliest arrival t_{ni}^a of eVTOL n at origin of passenger i and value v_{ni} of serving $v_{ni} = d_{P_n, O_i} - \frac{p_i}{100}$
 - 7: **if** $t_{ni}^a < t_a[r]$ **and** capacity is feasible at O_i and D_i and $v_{ni} < v_{\text{best}}$ **then**
 - 8: $v_{\text{best}} \leftarrow v_{ni}, i_{\text{best}} \leftarrow i$
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **if** $i_{\text{best}} \neq -1$ **then**
 - 12: Assign request: $A[i_{\text{best}}] \leftarrow n$
 - 13: Update total profit: $p \leftarrow p + p[i_{\text{best}}]$
 - 14: Update capacities of vertiports over time based on eVTOL route
 - 15: Update eVTOL position to destination of chosen request and availability time
 - 16: **end if**
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: **end for**
 - 19: **Output:** Assignments A , Total profit p
-

In the following case study, we will use the presented heuristic to solve the second stage of

the AOS framework.

5. Numerical case study

In this section, we present a case study of the Community of Madrid and Adolfo Suárez Madrid-Barajas Airport (Madrid Airport hereinafter), based on real-world data and inputs from experts, to demonstrate the performance of the developed AOS framework. With extensive numerical experiments, we obtain managerial insights regarding the applicability of our framework, as well as practical insights on the distribution of vertiports and the fleet size of eVTOLs. Since this paper is a part of the Multimodal Access for Intelligent Airports (MAIA) project (Horizon Europe grant number 01114853), all major assumptions and input data and parameters were subject to evaluation by experts from different stakeholder groups (airports, air traffic management, consultancy in mobility, city officials and academia) during two workshops and one dedicated UAM webinar with a follow-up survey.

5.1. Passenger data

We use actual passenger demand data, that is, passengers going to or from Madrid Airport for one day in April 2024. For instance, Madrid Airport had 5.4 million pax during April 2024, and 66.2 million during 2024, ranking it 5th among European airports in terms of PAX numbers in 2024. We are not using peak demand periods to test and evaluate capacity decisions to reflect the average usage over the year. Anonymized passenger data is obtained from a mobile network data (MND) and consists of records of interactions between mobile devices and the network of antennas managed by a mobile network operator as described in Bueno-González et al. (2024). The analysis of MND as explained by Blasco-Puyuelo et al. (2022); Burrieza-Galán et al. (2022), allows to extract the passenger origin to and destination from the airport with a precision on a mobile antenna cell level, as well as the associated departure and arrival times to/from the airport.

Based on the analysis of passenger (mobile) data, we conclude that passenger demand is almost the same for both Terminals 1/2/3 and Terminal 4 systems, which we further validate by comparing the findings against Aena's (airport operator) statistics on the number of commercial passengers by destination for 2024.

5.2. Vertiport locations and capacity

Geographically, the passenger data covers the community of Madrid area where 85% of the airport access demand comes from or gravitates to. This area is within approximately 50 kilometers from the airport, which we assume as a maximum range for the design eVTOL aircraft. In the dataset, we include 356 different neighbourhoods (barrios) for which we derive demand distributions over the days. We consider the possibility that each centroid of these 356 different zones could be a potential vertiport location, which is in line with the usual assumptions in the literature, e.g. by Rimjha et al. (2021).

For the vertiports in the urban area we assume multifunctional Final Approach and Take Off (FATO), i.e., single-pad as in Preis (2021). The multifunctional FATO that is used for landing and take-off operations is also used for the eVTOL turnaround process - passenger disembarking/embarking and battery charging. HERNICZEK et al. (2024) and Ahn and Hwang (2022) arrange multiple multifunctional FATOs along the same line, with safe separation between two adjacent multifunctional FATOs to allow independent operations. Preis (2023; 2021) combines such multifunctional FATOs to provide safe separation between any FATO pair, and suggest a maximum number of FATOs in this arrangement of four. To evaluate the demand potential, we assume one possible vertiport with 3-5 independent multifunction FATOs per neighbourhood (zip code hereinafter).

At the airport side, we consider ten potential vertiport locations as shown in Figure 2:

- Two airside locations near Terminals 1, 2 and 3 - portion of GA apron (A1), and isolated apron (A2).
- Portion of apron area in Terminal 4 zone (A3).
- Two car parks near Terminals 1,2 and 3, smaller (L1), larger (L2) and taxi (L7).
- Two car parks (L3, L6), one unpaved adjacent area (L5) and one rooftop of the parking garage (L4) near Terminal 4.

For instance, see MORSHECK et al. (2025); Ahn and Hwang (2022); FELDHOFF and ROQUE (2021) for selected vertiport locations at airports in Frankfurt, Gimpo (Seoul) and Cologne Bonn Airports, respectively.

Figure 2: Possible vertiport locations at Madrid airport

All areas at Madrid airport are large enough, ranging from 11500 m^2 at A1 to 82500 m^2 at L5, to house hub vertiports with capacity far exceeding maximum potential demand which we evaluated with several random scenarios. Therefore, we do not limit the capacity of vertiports at airport, i.e., it is mathematically unconstrained in the model.

5.3. Travel times

As expressed in Section 5.1, MND allows to extract the origin/destination of the airport trips at antenna level. However, for the purpose of this study, specific coordinates are required. Therefore, a disaggregation process has been performed to assign specific origin/destination coordinates to each MND-detected trip which considers the coverage of the antenna and land use data. The origin/destination coordinates of the passenger trips have been assigned to the 356 neighborhoods.

For our demand choice model (see Section 5.4), we have calculated the travel time (in minutes) by car from every neighbourhood to the ten nearest possible vertiport locations in the adjacent zones. This is necessary since our vertiport network will not have a vertiport in each zone, so passengers need to take a car to reach the nearest built vertiport. For the calculation of travel times, a simplification of the process has been applied. The study zoning has been divided into

a 100 m x 100 m grid, and travel times from the centre of the grid to the vertiports has been calculated using Open Streets Maps API. As a result, all passengers whose origins or destinations fall within the same grid cell will share identical travel times. For each of these grid zones, we generate a synthetic population based on the distributions obtained from the real data to estimate realistic ground travel times of passengers to the centroids of each zone, at which the potential vertiport is located.

We evaluate the impact on results of four potential eVTOL cruise speeds: 100, 120 150 and 200 km/h, since this aspect of eVTOL performance has the highest impact on flight time. The lower end of speed spectrum is for so called multicopter eVTOLs, such as eHANG 216, AirbusCity, Volocopter, etc. while higher speeds are associated to lift and cruise and vectored thrust eVTOLs such as Vertical Aerospace VX4 and Joby. For rates of climb and descend we use values between 500 ft/min and 1,500 ft/min and assume that hover, transition to climb and climb phases will be completed in 90 seconds to preserve battery, with the average climb speed equal to 60% of cruise speed (same for descend and landing phase). Following the computational experiment, we approximate eVTOL travel times with piecewise linear functions for each cruise speed, which is the variable with the highest impact on travel times. A detailed review of the current technical state of autonomous eVTOLs can be found in Xiang et al. (2024).

There are several route design options between the urban area and airport for UAM airport shuttle service. For instance, the last edition of Federal Aviation Administration Concept of Operations (Federal Aviation Administration, 2023) indicates that eVTOLs will use existing and published helicopter routes in the initial phases with gradual development of route and network design. Since UAM route length directly impacts eVTOL flight times, it is important to assess the assumptions we need to make to determine UAM route lengths. We designed and evaluated more than 20 different routes between different potential vertiport pairs between Community of Madrid area and Madrid Airport (e.g., over the Madrid Ring roads, major streets and areas with lower human activities). Such routes were between 15% and 40% longer than the shortest/direct routes, and we decided to test and evaluate the impact of three different scenarios for route network design: shortest distance and scenarios with 10% and 30% route extension compared to shortest, to account for any potential constraints across the urban area.

Moreover, we use four different scenarios which account for different requirements for additional times such as battery charging, passenger embarking, disembarking, briefing, etc. of 5,

7, 12 and 17 minutes between flights. In the literature, passenger processing time ranges from 30 s to 10 min, and battery charging from 0 to 30 min (Mirković and Sindik, 2024). We start with 7 min (5 min briefing plus 1 min for both disembarking and embarking). For our sensitivity analysis, we also use 5 min (Uber's scenario described by Macias et al. (2023)), 12 min (baseline plus 5 min extra waiting/charging time), 17 min (baseline plus 10 min extra waiting/charging time).

Lastly, we calculate the times needed for passengers arriving from airport vertiports to respective terminal buildings. Based on the vertiport locations we use the distance via public roads and driving speed 30 km/h for landside vertiports located on the airport, and the distance via apron service roads, and driving speed 20 km/h for airside locations.

5.4. Financial assumptions

In this subsection, we present our financial assumptions for the case study. On the revenue side, we use a cost-plus-profit pricing strategy of the operators assuming a fixed revenue of the eVTOL service per passenger kilometer of 5 Euro, based on the analysis of Berger and Center (2024), and cost estimates from Goyal et al. (2018). The average cost of service per passenger-kilometer depends on many different assumptions and ranges from as low as 1 Euro per passenger mile to relatively high 15 Euro. Note that the reviewed academic publications tend to use lower cost values, while the assumed cost per kilometer in our study tend to be more in the middle range (Berger and Center, 2024).

To estimate the profit of daily operations, we assume a profit margin of 20% which is also used in the NASA study by Goyal et al. (2018) and is the profit margin for the fiscal year 2024 for the above mentioned Blade helicopter company (Blade Air Mobility, 2021).

To calculate the daily depreciation cost of both one vertiport and one eVTOL to assess the simplified profitability of the service, we use an estimated price of 300,000 Euro per eVTOL. For the cost of eVTOLs we assume the lowest published price of eHANG 216 aircraft in 2024, the only certified eVTOL in the world, more precisely in China, as reported in the media outlets such as by Flight Global (Chua, 2024). A planned 10-year usage yields a daily depreciation cost of 83 Euro.

Vertiport cost may include many sub-costs like land acquisition, site preparation and construction, permits, equipment, etc. Some vertiports in urban and suburban areas may also require

terminal building. This is not the case with airport vertiport which uses airport passenger terminals for any extra processing, or urban vertiports that target shorth waiting time, i.e., as direct as possible vehicle-to-vehicle transfer.

In this study, we estimate vertiport cost based on electrical charger's unit price of roughly 500,000 Euro, based on NASA study by Black and Veatch and National Institute of Aerospace (2018), and the number of multifunctional FATOs, which we vary between 3 and 5. The price increases and decreases linearly with the number of multifunctional FATOs implemented in one vertiport. In this case, we assume that the infrastructure will be subsidized to an extent, as suggested in the literature by Mendonca et al. (2022) and announced in practice by, e.g., the Japanese government to subsidize vertiports up to 50% of the construction cost (The Japan Times, 2024).

We start with an optimistic scenario in which governments and cities will subsidize 75% of the urban vertiport cost leading to a total price of 500,000 Euro for 4 multifunctional FATOs, yielding a daily depreciation cost of 183 Euro for a 10-year usage. In our numerical experiments, we will also test a pessimistic case in which there are no subsidies for vertiport construction costs. This means the UAM airport shuttle service providers covers four times higher cost for each vertiport than in our base case leading to a cost of 2,000,000 Euro per vertiport with 4 multifunctional FATOs. The cost of building a vertiport at airport site is considered to be zero since we assume the airport operators want to incentivize UAM airport shuttle service providers to implement their service. Lastly, we assume no budget constraints, so B is set to infinite.

5.5. Passenger demand and demand choice modelling

In our numerical simulation, we model the demand for an eVTOL shuttle service over a period of one day as an average of the available data of seven days. We consider only one day since airport flight data show that there is only very limited seasonality across months and days of the week for business and first-class passengers who are the main target group for this type of service.

Since there is no real-world data on an airport shuttle service operated by a fleet of eVTOLs and the focus of our paper is on the usability of the developed mathematical modelling framework and not on a complex demand choice model, we build a simple demand model based on the following assumptions and considerations. Our demand assumptions were discussed and aligned

with industry and airport practitioners in workshops, as already noted in the beginning of this section.

We assume that the demand per zip code is based on the overall demand of passengers traveling to and from the airport. We develop two overall uniform probability distributions of UAM usage, one applicable for zip codes with an average income within the highest 25 percentile of income, and one for zip codes with an average income within the 75th percentile. We use the average income of the passengers provided by their origin zip codes. Zip codes with higher income have higher demand than zip codes with lower income to reflect a higher willingness and ability to pay for a premium service. For Madrid, the UAM demand γ_l of the 75th percentile zip codes is sampled from a uniform distribution between 0.5% and 3.5% for each scenario as a usage rate. For the highest 25% income zip codes, demand γ_h is sampled from a distribution between 2% and 5% for each scenario. Our assumed demand share of 0.5 – 5% is taken from the analysis conducted by Coppola et al. (2024) and lies within a predominant range of other relevant literature, e.g., by Goyal et al. (2021); Choi and Park (2022); Mayakonda et al. (2020); Ploetner et al. (2020); Pukhova et al. (2021), while some industry reports tend to have much higher estimates for eVTOL market shares.

Based on this usage rate, we calculate the number of passengers traveling to/from the airport from/to a given zip code a over the time horizon of one day. We distribute the daily demand over the time stages using the temporal demand distribution of the zip code.

However, these arrival probabilities only hold true if there is a vertiport built at the origin of demand. In reality, there will not be a vertiport in every zip code but passengers have to travel on ground from their origin to the nearest built vertiport location. Therefore, we build a simplified demand model focusing on time sensitivity of passengers willing to use eVTOL based on total travel time using an eVTOL at the nearest built vertiport. The total travel time consists of three parts, which are the ground travel time from the demand origin O_i^C to a built vertiport O_i $d_{O_i^C O_i}$, the eVTOL travel time to the airport vertiport D_i $d_{O_i D_i}$ and lastly the ground travel time (by foot, shuttle, car) from the airport vertiport to the airport terminal D_i^T $d_{D_i D_i^T}$.

$$d_{O_i^C D_i} = d_{O_i^C O_i} + d_{O_i D_i} + d_{D_i D_i^T} \quad (18)$$

For every zip code, we define a base scenario for the shortest and longest possible travel time to the airport and then use a non-linear descending function $P(\cdot)$ of type $P(x) = \eta + \frac{\zeta}{x}$ that depends on the time needed to get to the airport and which expresses the likelihood of a passenger to use

the offered UAM service. If there is no vertiport in any neighboring zone, passengers will not use UAM, $P(\cdot)$ is set to zero. We use the time needed when using the closest possible vertiport to set $P(x) = 1$ and the longest possible combination as $P(x) = 0.2$. With these two points, we determine the parameters η, ζ for the likelihood calculation.

If a customer arrives in a scenario (sampled with γ), we sample if they would still use the eVTOL shuttle service if the built vertiport is not the theoretically closest to them with the percentage provided by the formula.

5.6. Facility location problem benchmark algorithm

To assess the performance of our AOS framework, we compare it to a deterministic facility location problem benchmark. This benchmark removes all sources of uncertainty from the problem, providing an intuitive approach to tackle a vertiport placement problem. This benchmark is selected because it closely resembles our model structure, while neglecting the effect of uncertainty by assuming a deterministic demand. With this comparison, we demonstrate the benefits of our AOS methodology and highlight the added value of incorporating uncertainty into the decision-making process.

The number of eVTOLs is determined via a local search heuristic for this benchmark after the subset of vertiport locations has been determined. The facility location problem is displayed as a mixed integer program and solved with Gurobi in Python.

Let L be the set of potential locations for vertiports in the urban area which is identical to the number of zip codes. D_l represents the expected demand at zip code l , c_l the cost of placing a vertiport at location l and P_{lj} the probability that demand at zip code l is served by a hub at zip code j . We define a set of decision variables for the problem at hand: If a vertiport is placed at zip code l , x_l equals one, zero otherwise. If demand at location l is assigned to a vertiport at location j , y_{lj} equals one, zero otherwise.

The objective of the facility location problem is to maximise the total realized demand while minimising the total vertiport placement cost:

$$\max \sum_{l \in L} R_l p_l - c_l \cdot x_l, \quad (19)$$

with R_l being the realized demand at location l and p_l the profit of a passenger traveling from location l to the airport.

We introduce a set of constraints to ensure a feasible realization of demand:

$$R_l = \sum_{j \in J} D_l \cdot P_{lj} \cdot y_{lj} \quad \forall l \in L \quad (20)$$

$$y_{lj} \cdot M_l^{\max} \leq P_{lj} \cdot x_j \quad \forall l \in L, \forall j \in J \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} y_{lj} \leq 1 \quad \forall l \in L \quad (22)$$

$$y_{ij} \leq x_j \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J \quad (23)$$

$$x_l \in \{0, 1\}, y_{lj} \in \{0, 1\}, R_l \geq 0, \quad M_l^{\max} \geq 0. \quad (24)$$

Eq. (20) ensures that each zip code's realized demand depends on the assigned hub and its probability as discussed in the demand modelling section of the case study. Eq. (21) enforces that demand is assigned only to the vertiport with the highest probability among candidate vertiports denoted by M_l^{\max} . According to Eq. (22) and (23) each demand can be assigned to at most one candidate vertiport.

5.7. Numerical results and insights

Using the data and the demand model described above, we analyse the performance of our developed AOS framework and compare it with the facility benchmark presented in Section 5.6. For the AOS framework, we set the threshold $\lambda = 800$, a maximum number of $W_{max} = 500$ iterations, and a risk constraint of $\alpha = 0.15$. In a first numerical test for 1000 smaller instances, the proposed heuristic of the second-stage optimisation MIP (Subsection 4.2) reveals a gap of $\approx 2.5\%$ to the MIP optimal solution. We use the heuristic in the following to efficiently solve the second-stage optimisation problem.

We calculate the average daily profit of an eVTOL airport shuttle service for a so-called base scenario based on the characteristics discussed in the previous paragraphs. We assume a ground time of $d^g = 7$ min, an eVTOL speed of 100 km/h, and shortest routes between the vertiports. For this scenario, the framework determines 9 best vertiports including two vertiports at the airport site and 14 eVTOLs in operation, which yields an average daily profit of $\approx 2,592$ Euro. The locations of the zip codes, which were selected for locating vertiports in their respective centroids (or in proximity of zip code centres), are shown in Figure 3, the capacity of the vertiports ranges between 3 (for 5 vertiports) and 4 (for 2 vertiports) multifunctional FATOs. At the airport site, the

model selects two airside locations, L2 at Terminals 1,2,3 and L4 at Terminal 4, which confirm our view on the advantage of airside vertiports over landside vertiports at the airport.

Figure 3: Proposed vertiport locations for Madrid urban area show vertiports in high-income, business, tourist and rural areas

Of the seven selected zones for vertiport placement, four are in the city centre, closely located to high-income areas, business areas and tourist attractions including rail stations. One vertiport location is in the West of the city in another high-income area. Another vertiport location is in the North of the urban area, close to several major company headquarters. All of these placements are in line with expectations.

Contrary to expectations, there is a zone selected by the model in the less densely populated east of the urban area. Essentially, this vertiport aggregates demand from the eastern part of the Madrid province, which is counterintuitive to common expectations and assumptions for eVTOL shuttle services. It can be partially explained by the longer distance to the airport leading to higher profits and the ability of this zone to aggregate demand from all adjacent zones.

Insight 1: Although the majority of vertiports is located in either high-income, business or touristic areas, less densely populated areas also need to be considered by decision makers and

can drive profitability based on our experiments.

Currently, there is a high level of uncertainty regarding the ground times between two flights d^g due to ambitious fast-charging processes, necessary safety instructions for the passengers and other technical constraints. An analysis of the impact of ground time on the average profit can help decision makers prioritize technical solutions and assess the relevance of optimising ground processes. Our initial assumption is that ground times have a high impact on the average expected profit as well as the number of eVTOLs deployed and the capacity of the vertiports due to following reasons: First, the eVTOLs are occupied longer with one flight reducing the number of trips per day per eVTOL. Second, eVTOLs being on the ground for charging or handling customers, are occupying a multifunctional FATO for other arriving eVTOLs so that vertiports need more multifunctional FATOs to serve the same demand leading to higher costs. These constraints are more significant with increasing ground time.

We determine the best vertiport and eVTOL subset for different ground times and test this network with 10,000 demand scenarios. The results can be seen in Figure 4 for ground times of $d^g = 5, 7, 12, 17$ min. Our developed AOS framework shows a significant advantage over the facility location benchmark in all observed ground time scenarios with an increasing advantage with increasing ground time. Since the benchmark focuses on the expected demand for the optimal subset but neglects the operational second stage, it is not able to compete with our proposed framework. Moreover, the probability of a negative profit, bound by α in Eq. (2), is more than 80x higher in the benchmark setting with $\approx 1 - 4\%$ compared to $0 - 0.05\%$ when applying our framework.

As expected, the average network profit decreases with increasing ground time due to the above assumptions. However, contrary to our expectation, there is only very limited change in the vertiport capacities in the different best solutions. For a ground time of 5 and 7 min, the vertiport capacities are identical. For a ground time of 12 min, one vertiport capacity changes from 4 to 3 multifunctional FATOs and one capacity from 4 to 5 compared to the 7 min solution. If the ground time is increased to 17 min, the capacity of one vertiport changes from 3 to 4 compared to the 12 min solution.

The number of eVTOLs is 14 vehicles for a ground time of $d^g = 5$ and $d^g = 7$ min. For a ground time of 12 min, the number of vehicles increase by 2 to 16 vehicles. For a ground time of 17 min, 18 vehicles are deployed. A 2 min reduction in ground time only yields 2% higher

Figure 4: Increasing advantage of AOS framework over facility benchmark with increasing ground times

profits. Even more than doubling the ground times from 5 to 17 min reduces the average network profits by only 17%.

Insight 2: Increasing ground (turnover) times can be balanced by more eVTOLs and minor vertiport capacity adjustments. Shorter ground times have very limited effect on average network profits. Even if ground times are increased by > 100%, by deploying $\approx 30\%$ more eVTOLs, high profitability can be maintained.

To assess the importance of our introduced risk constraint in Eq. (2), we analyse a pessimistic scenario, as described in Subsection 5.4. Moreover, we increase the demand uncertainty by widening the demand distributions introduced in Subsection 5.5 to 0 – 4% for the 75th percentile zip codes and 1 – 6% for the 75th percentile zip codes. This scenario is highly relevant since it is unclear if, and to what extent, governments, cities, or airports will subsidize an eVTOL airport shuttle service and there is very high uncertainty in customer adoption.

We calculate the average expected daily profit with our facility benchmark, our AOS framework as well as with our model without Eq. (2) to investigate the different best solutions if we apply a model which hedges against risk compared to a model which aims to maximise profit without considering risk adversity. The results are displayed in Table 1. All models select vertiports with a capacity of 3 multifunctional FATOs. The number of vertiports represents vertiports in the urban area and the two selected vertiports at the airport site.

Method	eVTOLs	Vertiports	Average Daily Profit	Probability of a Loss	
Risk-averse framework	AOS	5	1+2	698	12.6%
No-risk framework	AOS	11	3+2	980	23.7%
Facility location benchmark	location	13	5+2	690	32.7%

Table 1: Advantage of risk-averse AOS framework in highly uncertain setting

The table highlights the importance of a risk-adverse framework in highly uncertain settings. The benchmark algorithm is not able to fully consider uncertain demand, it also does not account for the risk of over- or under-provisioning of capacities, leading to a high risk of negative profits of more than 30%. Our developed AOS framework, without risk adversity, is able to find better vertiport placements, leading to higher average profits while decreasing the risk of negative profits to 23.7%. However, this risk of unprofitability is still very high. Our risk-adverse AOS framework is capable of significantly hedging against this risk to lower than 15%, which is the set threshold, to in total a risk probability of 12.6%. However, risk hedging comes with lower average profits similar to the average profit of the benchmark algorithm.

Insight 3: Decision makers need to carefully choose their level of risk adversity. Our AOS framework is able to hedge against risk in highly uncertain settings. The method retains similar profits at significantly lower probability of making a loss, compared to the facility location benchmark.

In the following experiments, we investigate the impact of different settings influencing the eVTOL flight time, the maximum flight speeds of the chosen eVTOL model and the permitted routes between vertiports and airport, on the average daily profit of operations. Since these parameters only affect the flight time of eVTOLs, we set the capacity of our possible vertiport locations to 4 to focus on the impact of a variation of flight characteristics on the number of eVTOLs.

The first parameter influencing eVTOL flight time is the vehicle speed. While we assume a top speed of 100 km/h in our base scenario, some vehicle manufacturers promise higher speeds

in urban areas, as mentioned in Section 5.3.

If we assume an increase of the eVTOL top speed by 50% to 150 km/h, our experiments show a 10% profit increase compared to the base scenario if our proposed AOS framework is applied. The optimal subset also consists of 14 eVTOLs and 9 vertiports as the base scenario, with marginal differences in the vertiport locations.

A further increase to 200 km/h yields another 3.5% increase compared to the base scenario to a total advantage of 13.5%. Similar percentage differences are observed if the facility benchmark policy is applied. In this scenario, the optimal subset consists of 12 eVTOLs and 8 vertiports. The base case vertiport network for these two new scenarios yields similar results with an average daily profit only approx. 3% lower than if the optimal network is used.

Insight 4: Vehicle speed only has limited impact on operational profit, the impact is decreasing with higher speeds. Based on our analysis, prioritizing maximum allowable speed when selecting eVTOL models offers limited economic benefit. Even a doubling of the maximum speed only leads to \approx 15% smaller fleet.

The second parameter is the flight route. In our base scenario, we assume shortest distances between vertiports. However, policy makers might decide alternative eVTOL routes, e.g., to avoid fly-over of buildings or pedestrian areas, leading to longer distances and longer flight times, as mentioned in Section 5.3. In our simulation study, we analyse the impact of 10% and 30% longer routes on the average daily profit.

In a scenario with +10% route extension, the average profit decreases by less than 4% compared to the base scenario with the shortest routes. If the routes are further extended to +30%, the difference increases to 4.5% compared to the base scenario in the best vertiport network. We observe that the system tries to compensate for longer routes by using more eVTOLs with 16 eVTOLs used in the 30% setting instead of 14 eVTOLs in the base scenario, which is a 15% increase of fleet size. If the route extension is applied to the base case subset of vertiports, there is a 6% difference in profit in the +30% route extension scenario.

Insight 5: Route extensions, i.e., resulting from government-imposed airspace restrictions, have only minimal effect on the average daily profit. The system compensates for increased travel distances by deploying additional vehicles. Our experiments indicate that the number of vehicles grows at half the rate of route extension.

5.8. Analysis of leveraging existing heliports for eVTOL implementation

Our analysis has shown that vertiport infrastructure cost are a key driver of average profitability of our proposed eVTOL service. Given the uncertainty on infrastructure cost ranging from few hundreds thousands (early estimates) to several million Euro (driven by recent estimates for charger installation) and the availability of subsidies from governments or investors, it is a logical step to explore options for reducing any earlier mentioned additional cost (land acquisition, site preparation and construction, permits, etc.). One promising approach is to explore the potential use of existing heliports, which often already fulfil regulatory requirements for UAM and may be adapted for use as vertiports with comparatively little effort. If some of the neighbourhoods selected by the AOS framework coincide with heliport locations, significant reductions in deployment cost, regulatory complexity, and implementation time may be achievable. This subsection investigates to what extent existing heliport infrastructure in Madrid could be leveraged to support the proposed eVTOL airport shuttle service.

Figure 5: Majority of selected vertiport sites' zip codes contain existing heliports

To assess spatial overlap, we map existing heliports and their type onto the urban layout of Madrid (see Figure 5). The figure shows that only one of the selected neighbourhoods for

vertiports north of the airport contains an existing heliport. For the remaining six vertiports, we evaluate the possibility of using existing heliports in adjacent zip codes while trying to limit the negative impact of location changes on the average expected profit. Since we approximate the vertiport cost with the cost for electrical chargers, the cost for repurposing heliports is the same as for new vertiports.

Notably, there are two heliports close to the vertiport in the West of Madrid which could potentially be used as vertiports. Furthermore, the vertiports proposed in the North and South of the city centre could be replaced by adjacent existing heliports. If we consider these three chosen heliports as alternatives to our proposed vertiport locations, the expected average profit is only 12.5% lower than in the original base scenario using optimised new vertiport locations. For the remaining four vertiport locations, there is no suitable existing heliport in adjacent zip codes without diminishing profits by more than 15 – 20%.

Insight 6: The partial exploitation of existing heliport infrastructure results in only a small decrease in profitability, suggesting a viable path to cost reduction and accelerated implementation without significantly compromising network performance. Decision makers have to balance the positive cost effect of using existing infrastructure with the negative impact on operational profits due to non-optimal locations.

Beyond cost and time savings, the use of existing heliport infrastructure can also increase public awareness and acceptance, while simplifying regulatory processes. However, it is important to mention that this is a conceptual high-level analysis. The actual feasibility of converting heliports into vertiports, with a perspective of co-usage by both modes of transportation, depends on many factors, such as physical available space, power supply and compliance with future regulations, and is difficult to assess. A more detailed, site-specific investigation and knowledge of future eVTOL regulations will be essential to validate these assumptions.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we have developed a framework to optimise an eVTOL airport shuttle service by defining the best vertiport network and number of eVTOLs in operation. We have modeled the problem as a two-stage risk-averse newsvendor problem and solved the second stage MILP with a simple heuristic approach. We have shown that our approach outperforms a facility benchmark algorithm in several scenarios and derived actionable insights for decision makers.

Our work contains some limitations and assumptions, offering various directions for future research. In our work, the operational phase does not include active fleet rebalancing. Future works could explore active rebalancing mechanisms to assess the impact on the number of flights and average profit. This will increase the complexity of the second stage of the newsvendor problem requiring more complex approximations.

Within our model, we explicitly account for uncertain materialization of demand for UAM airport shuttle service, but we presently do not consider uncertainties associated with capacity. Namely, vertiport capacity is stochastic by nature and there are many factors which may impact it. For instance, lower capacity usability due to meteorological conditions could impact the reliability of UAM services and the volume of demand that can be effectively served. Another avenue for improvement is to also include limitations of the U-space capacity; that problem would be similar to the air traffic flow and capacity management problem as defined in Künnen et al. (2023), where capacity constraints do not only hold in the nodes, but also on the 'arcs' of the U-space network.

The developed mathematical model could be used to include other UAM services, for instance air taxi in the city or between cities, transportation of goods, as well as medical, firefighter and other publicly relevant and important services. An adjusted model could include a fleet mix with different eVTOL types and sizes.

With the further development and testing of eVTOL fleets, our work may be enriched by more precise technical parameters and constraints regarding, e.g., possible ground times or vehicle speeds enabling further profitability analyses.

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